

THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN TECHNIQUES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING TO ESL STUDENTS

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Annotation. World globalization sets more rigid prerequisites for highly specialized school graduates. Other than proficient capabilities including a specific number of abilities a cutting-edge expert should not exclusively be an expert in his/her field however in consistency with the Government State Instructive Norms of Higher Expert Schooling can peruse unfamiliar logical and specialized writing, figure out fundamental data and legitimately apply the outcomes in his expert movement both in local and foreign languages. The learners' degree of dominating the language straightforwardly relies upon the showing strategies being utilized.

Keywords: teaching methods, foreign language education, higher education.

Introduction. Throughout the long term, there were different techniques for foreign language education, showing objectives and targets, schools, and instructing approaches. The new showing strategies were created because of the interest of the state from the beginning and society later in foreign language learning. The researchers attempted to track down the general showing technique in various sciences: Reasoning, Brain science, Semantics, and so forth. These days the foreign language educator at secondary school is to assist learners with remedying the holes in their language information in a brief time frame and shows them involving the foreign language as a device for getting proficient information and abilities too. It ought to be referenced that the hypothesis and practice information on foreign language instructing at different stages empowers the educator “to see the deliberate idea in the expansive instructive possibility,” and join various techniques and approaches in the work, considering their benefits and impediments. The accompanying researchers concentrated on the historical backdrop of foreign language instructing strategies: B. Bjorkman, K. A. Ganshina, N. I. Gez, G. O. Hellekjær, B. Kumaravadivelu, V. E. Raushenbakh, Jack Richards, E. Roulet, L. V. Shsherba, F. C. Sierra. Academician A. A. Miroljubov made an incredible commitment to foreign language showing techniques organizing, having distributed his book “The Historical backdrop of Local Foreign language Instructing Strategies”.^[1]

¹ Belyaev B.V. Essays on the psychology of teaching foreign languages <http://gigabaza.ru/doc/73625-pall.html>

As indicated by the investigation of logical academic and deliberate writing, foreign language learning can be followed back to the old days. In her book “Concentrated on in Rus. History of Training in Russia” Olga composes that generally in 988 A.D. 300 kids were taken “to be educated learned”. The first “erudite instructors” were Greek clerics welcomed uniquely to show Russian individuals the Greek language. The instructing had a commonsense nature, as the spreading of the new world viewpoint required proficient individuals who had the option to interpret and modify ceremonial books. The nation required informed ministers to talk not Greek and Latin yet the local language reasonable to the Russian public. Throughout the long term, Russia was transforming into an incredible power with created exchange joins. In the eighteenth century, the Russian state required ministers as well as specialists, traders, and administration classes. During the rule of Peter, the Incomparable an extraordinary number of instructive foundations (exceptional schools, proficient and old-style schools) were opened.

Their point was not exclusively to prepare experts for the state and church but to prepare gifted specialists in different fields (sailors, developers, workers, interpreters). It was in these years that the learning of Latin and old Greek was trailed by the learning of an extra foreign language that turned into the authority instructive subject. Latin, be that as it may, stays the norm of systematicity and consistency as in the past, the educating of “living” language was the language structure writing technique given (XVIII-XIX). The advocates of this school V. Humboldt, D. Hamilton, and G. Ollendorf believed the language to be a framework and since the sentence structure was the most deliberate language level, in showing the accentuation was made on careful linguistic framework language learning. Additionally, the need of gaining syntax came about because of the predominant assessment that language mirrored the rationale of reasoning, and consequently, sentence structure practices figured out how to think.

The foundation of training was the composed language since just it mirrored the genuine language. Subsequently, the texts were the fundamental material the instruction depended on, P. Gleizer and EH. Petrol expressed that “The texts for reading were picked by their reasonableness to mirror the punctuation material being concentrated on in the most ideal way.” A few defenders of this technique considered the instructive text content to spurn yet not to draw in schoolchildren for concentrating on language structure dominating the syntax,

not the text was significant. To control the degree of understanding syntax the learners were to decipher from the local language, the sentences not being associated with one another in the importance: “Lions, bears, and elephants are solid”, “This bear has a niece and a nephew”, “These camels composed their example of Russian language”. The jargon was viewed as just the outline for syntax learning. The words were prescribed to learn inappropriately as secluded units since they should contrast from one another simply by sound and realism but not by importance, similarity, and so forth.

Regardless of the way that this strategy made it conceivable to comprehend the syntax of the language being advanced completely it couldn't give rudimentary open abilities. The learners could barely offer their viewpoints and couldn't speak with the local speakers. Additionally, interpreting in the same words is off-base because definite writing is absurd or right all the time. In addition, writing is these days thought about as a file of one's language capability. Toward the finish of the eighteenth hundred years, there seemed an assortment of syntax writing strategies - text-based writing techniques. As for the agents of this technique, the preparation objective was the learners' general improvement in reading old-style writing. The substance and elaborate highlights of the text turned out to be more significant. In certain course readings, there was the line plan of the texts: in the main line there was a text in a foreign language, in the second line there was its record and the third line contained its strict writing, with the punctuation structure being equivalent to in the foreign language.^[2]

Having rehashed the text after the instructor commonly and having perused the record the learners were to dissect the writing and propose the proper writing. Subsequently, the articulation was drilled, and the investigation, jargon, and sentence structure learning were done. Not at all like the agents of the language structure writing strategy, the advocates of the literary writing technique didn't concentrate on the syntax exhaustively they utilized and dissected just the material that was in the text. Hence, the syntax instructing was unpredictable. The jargon, as in the past, was framed by the machine learning of discrete words and texts in the unfamiliar language. The delegates of this technique, nonetheless, made an extraordinary commitment to the language showing strategies having utilized interestingly the writing from the local language into the unfamiliar one. We very concur with the finishes of the writers of the book

² Bik E.A The Analitico-Synthetic Method of Foreign Language Teaching / Russkaya shkola. – 1890. - p5.

“Foreign language Showing Strategies at the Optional School” that without precedent for the historical backdrop of showing techniques the writing strategies for foreign language instructing had serious disadvantages.

First and foremost, they were gravely coordinated towards the language obtaining as correspondence implies in any event, for understanding preparation. The principal task was just broad training, it being perceived as the improvement of consistent reasoning because of punctuation learning and as the overall improvement because of coincidental sentence structure picking up during message examination. Besides, the trademark component of these strategies was structure and content division. In the punctuation writing technique, all consideration was centered around the structure, with the substance being dismissed. In the printed writing technique, the texts were not generally accessible since the punctuation was concentrated unsystematically and the learners were severely ready for its discernment. [3]

Thirdly, language learning depended on the sentence structure and rationale recognizable proof, on the dead language acknowledgment as the ideal, and the dismissing of the living dialects' explicit highlights. Toward the finish of the nineteenth century, writing strategies were supplanted by the immediate techniques for foreign language education. Their primary objective was to dominate the oral correspondence. In their book (Foreign language Showing Strategies at the Auxiliary School) the writers express that other than the current social-financial circumstances the quest for new showing techniques and approaches was brought about by the combination of such sciences as Brain research and Etymology. In Phonetics, there seemed another mental school headed by a language specialist and clinician Hermann Steinthal. The actual school didn't impact the showing techniques yet it turned into the halfway connection between the coherent school (it concentrated on the language in its connection to thinking and information) and the neogrammarian school (it considered the language as an individual psychophysical and psychophysiological action).

The neogrammarian school made an incredible impact on the language instructing hypothesis. The researchers of this school concentrated on the likenesses in the language in light of the mental relationship in the psyche of the individual talking. The accomplishments in Brain research additionally impacted

³ Billows F. L. The techniques of language teaching. London: Longman, 1961, DOI: 10.2307/321360

the immediate strategy advancement. In progress gave to the language the organizer behind the exploratory brain science W. Wundt, being a supporter of the associanism, expressed that the discourse was a sort of action where acoustic and motoric sensations were of incredible significance. During talking the sentence emerges in the man's awareness as an essential item. This belief is followed in the regular technique defender idea who believed the sentence to be the focal point of an oral assertion. One more strategy was addressed by the Würzburg school concentrating on the man's reasoning and its structures. The researchers of this school expressed the suggestion was neither associated with discourse nor with tactile insight. The discourse was to be shown mechanically.

Conclusion. Thus, to the extent that we can see during all its set of experiences the foreign language showing techniques changed a lot of times underscoring reading, interpreting, or tryout or joining these cycles. Every technique has its sure significance and answers the explicitly set educational undertakings for example syntax and literary writing techniques are more qualified for sentence structure material preparation before tests, direct strategies are more fitting for language medium submersion and for recreating the genuine correspondence circumstances, visual guides help to address outwardly and to systemize the obscure material. Based on the previous we can infer that during the entire history of foreign language showing techniques improvement methodologists and instructors featured various sorts of discourse exercises (reading, listening, writing) zeroing in on a specific period objective.

Also, every strategy has its particular worth and answers to explicit educational goals set. Accordingly, historiographical examination of foreign language showing strategies has formatted recognizing ways of coordinating various techniques in the act of language schooling. From our perspective, for learners learning at the specialized divisions, it would be helpful to apply sentence structure text-based deciphered strategies for clarification and modification of the language materials at the pre-message stage. Immediate and open techniques can be utilized to animate correspondence circumstances in the language climate. Also, utilizing perception devices assists with introducing and sorting out new material and making an external help of discourse acts.

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